

TRANSMISSION DYNAMICS AND MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF *BARTONELLA* IN INVASIVE *RATTUS* FROM SOUTH AFRICA

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Introduction

Bartonellosis encompasses a broad range of diseases and clinical symptoms caused by bacteria of the species-rich genus *Bartonella*. Three discrete species have been identified in *Rattus* from South Africa, of which one, *Bartonella elizabethae* has known zoonotic potential. Brettschneider *et al.* (2012) developed a model to study the dynamics of *Bartonella* transmission related to host and ectoparasite vector aspects. However, the model was based on limited data for a number of crucial biological parameters and was unable to explain the differential infection rates observed. The present study attempts to refine the initial model by obtaining empirical estimates for the biological parameters that had to be estimated, based on general rodent data, rather than *Rattus*-specific data. This will be achieved by a combination of molecular data and mathematical modeling approaches, the results of which will negate estimation of crucial biological parameters, and drive future biological research, respectively.

The aim of this study is to use molecular data to:

- Investigate potential vertical transmission and multiple infections of *Bartonella* in three *Rattus* species from South Africa.
- Investigate the prevalence of *Bartonella* in *Rattus*-borne ectoparasites.
- Incorporate additional revised parameters from this study into a mathematical epidemiological model (Brettschneider *et al* 2012).

Relevance of the study

The genus *Rattus* represents one of the most successful and destructive invasive mammalian species and shows a longstanding commensal association with humans. Beyond their natural distribution, they have a huge effect on endemic biodiversity which may lead to local extinction of some species. Additionally, they are known to pose a serious health risk by harbouring and spreading infectious diseases of human and animal health concern.

Bartonellae are transmitted by blood-feeding arthropods such as ticks, mites, fleas, lice and sand flies. There are two possible modes of transmission:

- Anterior station transmission (bites)
- Posterior station transmission (faeces)

Google.com

H. Brettschneider 2009

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Reference

Brettschneider, H., Anguelov, R., Chimimba, C.T. and Bastos, ADS. 2012. Journal of Biological Dynamics 6: 763-781

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Methodology

Sample collection

R. Julius 2012

R. Julius 2012

P. Tshikae 2012

P. Tshikae 2012

Molecular work and analyses

Individual rats were euthanized, identified, combed for ectoparasites and dissected. DNA was then extracted from heart samples of adults or from whole embryos. Samples were screened for *Bartonella* presence by PCR amplification of the *GItA* and *NuoG* gene regions. All positive samples were purified and sequenced. Phylogenetic analyses will be used to confirm bacterial species. Statistical analyses will also be used to further interpret data and refine biological parameters for the mathematical model.

Compartmental structure and flow-diagram of *Bartonella* infections in *Rattus* from South Africa (adopted from Brettschneider *et al.* 2012)

Results

Genus	Gender		Pregnancy status	No of pregnant females screened found to be <i>Bartonella</i> positive	Embryos screened for <i>Bartonella</i>	Vertical transmission rate
	females	males				
<i>Rattus</i>	82	74	35/82 (43 %)	19/35 (54 %)	38 (from 4 positive mothers)	23/38 (60.5%)

- A total of 325 rodents were collected from January-July 2012, from Gauteng Province in South Africa. Of these, 156 have been screened. The 60.5% *Bartonella* genome prevalence found in all tested embryos confirms that vertical transmission occurs in members of this invasive genus and provides valuable empirical data for an important model parameter.

Implications

The present study will assist medical, veterinary, municipal, conservation, and agricultural authorities in formulating strategies to manage problems associated with rodent pests.